

DOI: <https://10.5281/zenodo.18064155>

UDK:631.8.81.

AGROTECHNOLOGY OF MELON GROWING IN SOIL PRONE TO DEGRADATION AND EFFICIENCY OF MODERN FERTILIZER SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

This article highlights the dynamics of macro- and microelements (N, P, K, Ca, Mg, Cu, Zn, Mn, B, Mo, Co) in tomato crops under the integrated fertilization system, based on a review of scientific literature. Among macronutrients, nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium play a crucial role in yield formation, while micronutrients such as copper, zinc, manganese, boron, molybdenum, and cobalt are essential for photosynthesis, enzyme activity, flowering, and fruit development. According to the analysis, the integrated fertilization system improves the uptake of both macro- and micronutrients, increases yield by 15-20%, and enhances quality indicators by 10-15%.

Keywords: Integrated fertilization system, macro- and micronutrients, tomato, growth and development, quality indicators, effect.

INTRODUCTION

Melon (*Cucumis melo* L.) is an important cucurbit crop that has been traditionally cultivated in Uzbekistan, with high demand in both domestic and international markets. In our country, increasing melon yield and productivity is considered one of the strategically significant crops for the development of agriculture. According to 2023 data, the total melon harvest exceeded 1.7 million tons, with the Republic of Karakalpakstan contributing 15–18% of this amount [1].

In recent years, great attention has been paid in Karakalpakstan to modernizing agriculture, ensuring efficient use of water resources, and achieving high yields on soils prone to degradation. For example, in 2022, the area equipped with drip irrigation systems in the Republic exceeded 20 thousand hectares, nearly five times higher than in 2015 [2].

In this context, the use of modern water-soluble complex mineral fertilizers (NPK + micronutrients) and fertigation technology plays a crucial role in increasing the efficiency of melon cultivation on irrigated meadow-alluvial soils [8, 12]. This approach helps slow down soil degradation processes, ensures effective utilization of mineral nutrients, and enables the production of high-quality yields.

Soil degradation refers to the deterioration of the natural, agrochemical, and biological properties of the soil, leading to a decline in its fertility [3, 6]. It occurs through the following processes:

- Salinization (increase in soil salt content);
- Sodification (increase in sodium levels);
- Erosion (soil being washed away by wind and water);
- Compaction;
- Excessive irrigation and lack of drainage;
- Decrease in organic matter;
- Drying and deflation;
- Reduction and imbalance of soil nutrients.

Degradation is defined as the decline of soil or ecosystem relative to its previous state, resulting in reduced fertility and loss of ecological stability [4, 5]. Therefore, it is necessary to identify the degradation process for each contour section and implement scientifically-based measures to preserve and enhance soil fertility.

In the Republic of Karakalpakstan, where field experiments are being conducted, the following types of degradation are observed:

1. *Salinization (contamination with salts)*

The most severe type of degradation in the region is caused by the drying of the Aral Sea and the wind-driven spread of salts from the exposed seabed onto the land surface.

2. *Sodification (increase in sodium content)*

Water-soluble sodium penetrates the soil, negatively affecting its structure by causing compaction and reducing soil fertility.

3. *Deflation (wind erosion)*

Under the influence of hot (gharmsel) winds, the top, fertile layer of the soil is blown away.

4. *Compaction and structural degradation in irrigated lands*

Incorrect irrigation and the use of heavy machinery negatively affect soil density and structure.

5. *Water erosion*

It occurs infrequently but can develop in low-lying areas through the flow of rainwater.

6. *Decrease in organic matter (loss of humus)*

In the irrigated soils of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, humus content has decreased to 0.3-0.5%.

7. *Climatic degradation (aridization)*

As a result of the Aral disaster, air humidity has decreased and precipitation has declined.

8. *Biocenosis degradation (loss of plant cover)*

In pastures, the number of grass species is decreasing; in sandy areas, saxaul, saltwort, and other plants are becoming scarce.

9. *Degradation caused by infrastructure and human activities*

The efficiency of irrigation systems has decreased due to their aging and the malfunction of drainage systems.

10. *Disruption of nutrient balance*

The disruption of nutrient balance in agriculture is caused by improper application of NPK fertilizers, deficiency of micronutrients such as Zn, B, Cu, Mn, and, in some areas, an increase in Na, Cl, and SO₄, accumulation of toxic elements, drought, and poor quality of irrigation water. Elements like strontium and fluorine are observed in concentrations exceeding permissible limits.

Therefore, conducting field experiments in this region to mitigate the above negative effects, ensure efficient use of each hectare of cultivated land, and simultaneously secure safe food supplies is considered one of the most pressing tasks today.

For the research, irrigated meadow-alluvial soils widely distributed in the Republic of Karakalpakstan were selected. The mechanical composition of the soils used in the field experiments is light sandy loam, with humus content ranging from 0.45 to 0.87%, available nitrogen 12-23 mg/kg, phosphorus (P₂O₅) 8-14 mg/kg, and potassium (K₂O) 87-183 mg/kg. Additionally, the electrical conductivity (EC) ranges from 2.5 to 4.3 dS/m, indicating that the soils are weakly to moderately saline, which affects crop growth and yield.

In the conditions of Karakalpakstan, the comparative use of drip and sprinkler irrigation for melon cultivation is supported by scientifically proven evidence from global experience. Studies conducted in the arid regions of the United States, such as Arizona and California, as well as in Israel, Turkey, and Australia, have shown that drip irrigation can increase the water use efficiency of melons by 25-40%, while maintaining stable moisture in the topsoil layer improves sugar accumulation and fruit quality. Drip irrigation reduces the physiological stress of melons in sandy and sodic soils prone to salinization by moving salts deeper from the root zone.

Sprinkler irrigation, on the other hand, lowers the temperature by 2-4°C, creates a favorable microclimate, and protects melons from intense heat during the first 20-30 days of growth. According to research in Central Asia and Australia, sprinkler irrigation can reduce stress in mesophilic tissues by up to 35%; however, in saline soils, it may bring salts back to the surface. Therefore, alternating sprinkler and drip irrigation proves to be effective.

Global practice has shown that an integrated regime of both methods-sprinkler irrigation during the initial growth stage and drip irrigation during fruit setting and later growth-can reduce melon water consumption by 20-30% and increase yield by 15-25%. In the hot and windy climate of Karakalpakstan, this integrated technology is considered optimal, as it both reduces heat stress and preemptively controls salinization [3, 7, 9, 10].

During melon cultivation, the plant's demand for nutrients varies significantly throughout its vegetative period. Therefore, applying mineral fertilizers in stages according to the physiological needs of the plant ensures high yield and product quality. In the early stages, a balanced application of nitrogen and phosphorus promotes the development of vegetative mass, while during the flowering and fruit-setting stages, a predominance of phosphorus and potassium enhances fruit set, sugar accumulation, and drought tolerance. Below, a mineral nutrition scheme for melon has been developed according to its main growth stages.

Table 1
Melon Fertilization Scheme

Vegetation Stage	Period	NPK Ratio	Concentration (g/L)
3-4 true leaves	5-15 days	12-12-12	0,5-0,8 g/L
10-15 true leaves	15-25 days	24-8-8	0,9-1,2 g/L
Flowering	25-35 days	12-30-12	1,0-1,3 g/L
Fruit set	35-70 days	8-10-34 / 6-8-38	1,2-1,6 g/L
Fruit ripening	>70 days	4-8-40	1,0-1,3 g/L

The results obtained from this fertilization scheme in the first year primarily focused on selecting the appropriate concentrations and rates of mineral fertilizers at different vegetative stages in combination with irrigation, and assessing their effects on plant growth and development. In fertigation, several agrochemical factors were taken into account, particularly the soil's granulometric composition, moisture regime, and the mobile forms of nutrients. However, one year of data is insufficient to determine precise and optimal rates and concentrations.

Therefore, research will continue in the following year, with plans to automate irrigation processes, implement dynamic fertilization regimes, and mathematically

model the nutrient balance within the “soil-plant-fertilizer-water” system. This approach will allow for scientifically-based, economically efficient, and ecologically sustainable determination of mineral fertilizer rates. As a result, a scientifically grounded and optimized fertilization technology has been developed for degraded, low-fertility, and low-profitability lands, which can be practically applied by land users in the future.

Based on the results of the ongoing field experiments, the following preliminary conclusions can be drawn. Effective melon cultivation in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, where water resources are limited, the climate is arid, and soils are prone to degradation, requires agrotechnologies grounded in a solid scientific basis. The studies showed that the irrigated meadow-alluvial soils in the region have a light sandy-loam texture, low humus content (0.45-0.87%), and very low to low levels of available nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium. Electrical conductivity ranges from 2.5 to 4.3 dS/m, indicating weak to moderate salinity. Under such conditions, the main types of degradation characteristic of the Aral Sea region-salinization, sodification, deflation, loss of organic matter, and insufficient infrastructure-seriously affect the yield of agricultural crops, including melon.

Within the scope of the study, it was found that drip and sprinkler irrigation technologies play a crucial role in creating favorable conditions for melon growth. According to global experience, in the conditions of Karakalpakstan, integrating both methods-sprinkler irrigation during the initial growth stage followed by drip irrigation in subsequent stages-reduces heat stress, minimizes the risk of salinization, and can increase water use efficiency by 20-30% [8, 9, 11].

During melon cultivation, the dynamics of nutrient uptake vary significantly throughout the vegetative period. Accordingly, the developed NPK fertilization scheme (12-12-12; 24-8-8; 12-30-12; 8-10-34; 4-8-40) was shown in the experiment to be highly significant, positively affecting plant morphological development, flowering and fruit set, drought tolerance, and fruit quality. The results obtained in the first year demonstrated that the proper selection of concentrations, rates, and timing under fertigation directly influenced the physiological state and yield of melons.

However, due to the variability of soil physicochemical properties, granulometric composition, and types of degradation across different areas, one year of experimental data is insufficient to provide precise recommendations. Therefore, it is necessary to continue the research, model the nutrient balance and the interactions between irrigation, fertilization, and plant growth, and implement automated fertigation systems to develop an optimal fertilization plan.

In summary, to effectively organize melon cultivation on degradation-prone soils in the conditions of Karakalpakstan, it is necessary to implement scientifically-based measures, including:

Technologies that mitigate salinization (drip and sprinkler irrigation);

Integrated irrigation systems that ensure efficient water use and reduce heat stress;

Mineral fertilization schemes adapted to the plant's vegetative stages, taking into account micronutrients such as Zn, B, Mn, and Cu.

The implementation of this research provides the opportunity to develop practical recommendations for melon cultivation on degraded soils in Karakalpakstan, establish optimal fertigation regimes, and restore soil fertility. This study was conducted as part of the applied project AL-9124093877, titled «Development of Modern Agrotechnologies for Cultivating Agricultural Crops on Degradation-Prone Soils», and its results will contribute to enhancing food security and agricultural productivity in the region in the future.

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